

Utilization of Soymilk Residue for Wheat Flour Substitution in Gyoza skin

Authors : Naruemon Prapasuwannakul

Abstract : Soy milk residue is obtained as a byproduct from soy milk and tofu production with little economic value. It contains high protein and fiber as well as various minerals and phyto-chemical compounds. The objective of this research was to substitute soy milk residue for wheat flour in gyoza skin in order to enhance value of soy milk residue and increase protein and fiber content of gyoza skin. Wheat flour was replaced with soy milk residue from 0 to 40%. The soy milk residue prepared in this research contains 26.92% protein, 3.58% fiber, 2.88% lipid, 6.29% ash and 60.33% carbohydrate. The results showed that increasing soy milk residue decreased lightness (L*value), tensile strength and sensory attributes but increased redness (a*), yellowness (b*), protein and fiber contents of product. The result also showed that the gyoza skin substituted with 30% soy milk residue was the most acceptable ($p \leq 0.05$) and its protein and fiber content increased up to 45 % and 867 % respectively.

Keywords : Gyoza skin, sensory, soymilk residue, wheat flour

Conference Title : ICAFS 2014 : International Conference on Agricultural and Food Sciences

Conference Location : London, United Kingdom

Conference Dates : January 20-21, 2014